

Switching the conformation of 3,2':6',3''-tpy domains in 4'-(4-*n*-alkyloxyphenyl)-3,2':6',3''-terpyridine

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Figure S1. ESI mass spectrum of compound 8.

Figure S2. ESI mass spectrum of compound 9.

Figure S3. ¹H NMR spectrum (500 MHz, CDCl₃, 298 K) of compound **8**. Scale: δ/ ppm. * = residual CHCl₃.

Figure S4. ¹H NMR spectrum (500 MHz, CDCl₃, 298 K) of compound **9**. Scale: δ/ ppm. * = residual CHCl₃.

Figure S5. $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR spectrum (126 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K) of compound **8**. Scale: δ / ppm. * = CDCl_3 .

Figure S6. $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR spectrum (126 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K) of compound **8**. Scale: δ / ppm. * = CDCl_3 .

Figure S7. HMQC spectrum of compound **8** (^1H 500 MHz, ^{13}C 126 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K). Scale: δ / ppm. * = residual CHCl_3 or CDCl_3 .

Figure S8. HMQC spectrum of compound **9** (^1H 500 MHz, ^{13}C 126 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K). Scale: δ / ppm. * = residual CHCl_3 or CDCl_3 .

Figure S9. HMBC spectrum of compound **9** (^1H 500 MHz, ^{13}C 126 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K). Scale: δ / ppm. * = residual CHCl_3 or CDCl_3 .

Figure S10. HMBC spectrum of compound **9** (^1H 500 MHz, ^{13}C 126 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K). Scale: δ / ppm. * = residual CHCl_3 or CDCl_3 .

Figure 11. Solid-state FT-IR spectrum of compound **8**.

Figure 12. Solid-state FT-IR spectrum of compound **9**.

Figure S13. Head-to-tail (centrosymmetric) packing of 3,2':6',3''-tpy units in **6**.

Figure S14. Part of two layers in the crystal lattice of **8** in which C-H_{methylene}... π interactions contribute to the packing.

Figure S15. Space-filling representation of the packing diagram shown in the manuscript in Figure 8.

Figure S16. Space-filling representation of the packing diagram shown in the manuscript in Figure 10.